

IDEAL

INDOOR AIR QUALITY
HEALTH

Scientific Strategy of the cluster

IDEAL Project
Coordinators

Version 1.0
31 August 2023

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Cluster details

Cluster title	Indoor Air Quality and Health
Cluster acronym	IDEA/IDEAL
Dates and duration	September 1 st 2022 – August 31 st 2026 (48 months)
Horizon Europe call	HORIZON-HLTH-2021-ENVHLTH-02-02 Indoor air quality and health
Number of projects	7

IDEAL projects

PROJECT	TITLE	GA NUMBER
K-HEALTHinAIR	Knowledge for improving indoor air quality and health	101057693
SynAir-G	Disrupting Noxious Synergies of Indoor Air Pollutants and their Impact on Childhood Health and Wellbeing	101057271
LEARN	Evaluation on indoor air quality for children around Europe	101057510
TwinAIR	Indoor air quality for healthy living	101057779
InChildHealth	Identifying determinants for indoor air quality and their health impact in environments for children: measures to improve indoor air quality and reduce disease burdens	101056883
INQUIRE	Identification of chemical and biological determinants, their sources, and strategies to promote healthier homes in Europe	101057499
EDIAQI	Evidence Driven Indoor Air Quality Improvement	101057497

Cluster aim

The IDEAL cluster was created to optimise synergies, avoid overlaps and increase the impact of the projects selected for funding under the call *HORIZON-HLTH-2021-ENVHLTH-02-02 Indoor air quality and health*. The main cluster activities include the following:

1. Common cluster kick-off meeting of the participating projects
2. Annual cluster meetings and periodic reporting of joint activities
3. Common dissemination and communication activities
4. Thematic workshops/trainings on issues of common interest
5. Working groups on topics of common interest
6. Advisory board appointment

Document details

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Purpose	This document outlines the scientific strategy of the IDEAL cluster. It defines the Working Groups that were established according to topics of common focus of the cluster projects. The scientific strategy was discussed and agreed during the first three coordinator meetings between DG RTD and the cluster coordination team.

Revision history

The following table describes the main changes done in the document since it was created.

REVISION	DATE	DESCRIPTION	AUTHOR (PROJECT)
V.0.1	02.08.2023	First draft	SynAir-G and TwinAIR
V.0.2	18.08.2023	Review of the first draft	K-HealthinAIR
V.0.3	24.08.2023	Second draft	TwinAIR
V.1.0	29.08.2023	Final version	TwinAIR

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2. INTRODUCTION

The **Scientific Strategy** of the IDEAL Cluster outlines the scientific strategy of the cluster. It defines the Working Groups that were established according to topics of common focus of the projects. The scientific strategy was discussed and agreed during the first three coordinator meetings between DG RTD (represented by the cluster officer) and the cluster coordination team (formed by the individual project coordinators).

This document was jointly prepared by SynAir-G and TwinAIR projects - being the starting cluster coordinators - with feedback from all cluster projects. The scientific strategy provides an overview of the cluster composition and mandate decided by the project coordinators and the EC Officer. It also describes the cluster governance, the working groups that were created on practical topics of shared interest among the projects, the cluster annual meetings & thematic workshops, and the reporting activities. The composition of the cluster International Advisory Board is also included.

3. SCIENTIFIC STRATEGY

3.1 Cluster Structure

The IDEAL cluster was created to optimise synergies, avoid overlaps and increase the impact of the projects selected for funding under the call *HORIZON-HLTH-2021-ENVHLTH-02-02 Indoor air quality and health*. The cluster was officially established on 1 September 2022 and it will be active for 48 months (as the duration of most projects), until 31 August 2026.

It was first comprised of six Horizon Europe projects (101056883 INCHILDHEALTH, 101057271 SynAir-G, 101057693 K-HEALTHinAIR, 101057499 INQUIRE, 101057510 LEARN and 101057779 TwinAIR). A few months later the project 101057497 EDIAQI joined the Cluster.

It is agreed by all founding cluster members that the cluster may establish cooperation with other relevant ongoing and potential future initiatives.

3.2 Cluster Mandate

The cluster mandate was discussed with the project coordinators on 4th March 2022 and was a final version was distributed per email on 7th March 2022. The final version of the cluster mandate was included as a specific task in the Description of Action (DoA) of each project's grant agreement. It is described in the document 'Modalities of Implementation of the Cluster'. The common cluster activities are described in Table 1.

Table 1. Common cluster activities

Activity	Description
Common kick-off meeting	Organized in cooperation between DG R&I and the cluster.
Annual cluster meetings and periodic report of joint activities	To be delivered at each reporting period.
Common dissemination and communication activities	These activities include: Common dissemination and communication strategy of the cluster, Cluster web portal and visual identity, Cluster brochure, cluster newsletters, Shared Stakeholder List, Shared individual Data Management Plans, Policy Strategy of the cluster, Joint policy briefs and Scientific strategy of the cluster

The cluster deliverables with their delivery dates and lead projects are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. IDEAL cluster deliverables

Deliverable	Lead Project(s)	Delivery Date
Common web-portal and visual identity	K-HealthinAir	M9
Joint visual identity	LEARN	M9
Communication & Dissemination Strategy	LEARN, InChildhealth	M9
Social Media	TwinAIR, INQUIRE, SynAir-G	M13 (launch)

Cluster Brochure	INQUIRE	M12
Newsletter - No.1	LEARN	M18
Newsletter - No.2	TwinAir	M36
Newsletter - No.3	InChildHealth	M54
Policy Briefs	SynAir-G	M18, M32, M46
Shared stakeholder list	TwinAir	M18
Data Management Plans	TwinAir, INQUIRE	M12
Policy strategy of the cluster	SynAir-G, K-HealthinAir	M12
Scientific strategy of the Cluster	All projects	M12

3.3 Cluster Governance

According to the Modalities of Implementation of the Cluster, the cluster will be coordinated by the six project coordinators and their deputies (Cluster Coordinating Team). The cluster leadership will be rotated every 8 months, as indicated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. IDEAL cluster governance

The European Commission (DG RTD) is in charge of the oversight and good information flow, enabling joint agreements and long-term consistent development of the cluster. Initiated by DG RTD and the Cluster Coordination Team, triannual online meetings are being organised between the Cluster Coordination Team and DG RTD to discuss the progress of each project as well the of the working groups activities.

3.4 Cluster Working Groups

The Strategy of the Cluster was delineated in the document of the Cluster Modalities of Implementation and further discussed during the subsequent Coordinator meetings between DG RTD and the cluster coordination teams, that took place face to face on 10 October 2022 (kick-off meeting), and online on 12 December 2022, 22 March 2023 and 14 June 2023.

Following the kick-off meeting, a scoping exercise was performed to identify the topics of common focus and interests of the participating projects. All coordinators reported on these aspects, as shown in Table 3. From this exercise, it was concluded that there were several areas of common activity that would benefit from cooperation among the projects. This included microorganisms that are considered in the study (particularly bacteria and fungi), sensors both of chemicals and particulate matter, types of testing (e.g., in-vitro testing), health consequences (particularly respiratory and cognitive),

remediation strategies for air quality improvement (e.g., air filtration). Most projects focus on air quality effect on children and include schools (as well as houses, public transport means etc.) among the indoor spaces evaluated.

Participant engagement and risk assessment are not commonly focused by the cluster projects.

Table 3. Aspects related to IDEAL cluster per project

Project	Microorganisms considered		Sensors used for		In vitro testing
	Bacteria and Fungi	Virus	Chemicals	PMs	
InChildHealth	X	X	X	X	X
INQUIRE	X		X	X	X
K-HealthinAir	X		X	X	X
LEARN	X		X	X	X
SynAirG	X	X	X	X	X
TwinAIR	X	X	X	X	X

	Outcome type				Remediation Strategy		Risk Assessment
	Respiratory	Cognitive	Other	Biomarkers	Air filtration	Other	
InChildHealth	X	X			X	X	X
INQUIRE	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
K-HealthinAir	X	X			X	X	
LEARN		X		X	X		
SynAirG	X	X		X	X		
TwinAIR	X	X			X		X

	Participant engagement		Focus on children		Pilot study types				
	Questionnaires	Other	Cohort	Cases	Schools	Houses	Public Buildings	Hospitals or nurseries	Outdoor
InChildHealth	X	X	X		X	X	X		X
INQUIRE	X		X	X		X			X
K-HealthinAir	X				X	X	X	X	
LEARN			X		X				X
SynAirG		X	X	X	X				
TwinAIR	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X

The above priorities complemented by the discussion during the meetings, led to the agreement of establishing several working groups towards the implementation of the Cluster scientific strategy. These groups include topics related to Policy, Communications, Data management, Guidelines and Standards, Sensors, Health Outcomes and In-vitro models. Table 4 summarizes the seven cluster Working Groups with their respective WG leaders.

Table 4. IDEAL cluster Working Groups

Working Group	Lead Project
1. Science translation for policy and practice	SynAirG, K-HealthinAir
2. Data analysis/management and protection	TwinAir, INQUIRE
3. Communication and Dissemination	Inchildhealth, LEARN
4. Guidelines	SynAir-G
5. Sensors	INQUIRE

6. Health outcomes	SynAir-G
7. In-vitro models	LEARN

The European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) is collaborating with WG2 on Data analysis/management and protection to facilitate the harmonisation of data collection and format compatibility with Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring (IPCHEM). Other WGs may also collaborate with relevant institutions and authorities, as may be decided along the way.

It was agreed that the Working Groups will meet regularly to identify potential synergies. It was also agreed that the workshops planned within the Cluster operation will take place after the first year and following the needs and requests of the Working Groups as well as the progress of their work.

The Working Group leaders are invited to the regular Coordinator meetings, where they report their progress.

3.5 Cluster Annual Meetings and Thematic Workshops

The Cluster Coordination Team will organise at least four thematic workshops of common interest. Nevertheless, additional workshops may be further organized if deemed necessary or desirable. The themes and projects responsible for the workshops are under discussion within the Cluster and the time plan annual meeting and workshop plan is to be finalised by the end of September 2023.

3.6 Cluster Reporting

Each project will include in its Periodic Report a common chapter on cluster activities. This chapter will be prepared by the Cluster Coordination Team, under the leadership of the rotating cluster leaders. In this report, a description of the work developed by the WGs will be included. The responsible projects for each reporting period are:

- First periodic report: SynAirG / TwinAir (M1-M18);
- Second periodic report: InChildHealth / LEARNN (M19-M36);
- Final periodic report: K-HealthInAir / INQUIRE (M37-M48).

A 2–3-hour meeting will take place between the cluster projects and DG RTD after the end of each reporting period to present the deliverables that have been submitted as part of the cluster activities.

3.7 Cluster International Advisory Board

The International Advisory Board (IAB) will connect the cluster to significant initiatives in the field of indoor air quality and provide scientific and policy related advice. The IAB comprises 6 members nominated from the IAB of the projects and covering specific areas identified as key areas by the cluster coordinators. IAB composition was decided by the Cluster Coordination Team in month 6. Table 5 presents the composition of the International Advisory Board.

Table 5. Composition of IDEAL Advisory Board

Name	Country	Proposed by
Constantinos Sioutas	USA	InChildHealth
Sophia Spiliotis	Germany	KHealthInAir

Stylianos Kephelopoulos	Italy, IPCHEM	EC
Argyris Tzouvelekis	Greece	TwinAIR
Carlos Santos-Burgoa	USA	LEARN
Joeri Rogelj	UK	SynAir-G

IDEAL

INDOOR AIR QUALITY
HEALTH

CLUSTER POLICY STRATEGY

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Cluster details

Cluster title	Indoor Air Quality and Health
Cluster acronym	IDEA/IDEAL
Dates and duration	September 1 st 2022 – August 31 st 2026 (48 months)
Horizon Europe call	HORIZON-HLTH-2021-ENVHLTH-02-02 Indoor air quality and health
Number of projects	7

IDEAL's projects

PROJECT	TITLE	GA NUMBER
K-HEALTHinAIR	Knowledge for improving indoor air quality and health	101057693
SynAir-G	Disrupting Noxious Synergies of Indoor Air Pollutants and their Impact on Childhood Health and Wellbeing	101057271
LEARN	Evaluation on indoor air quality for children around Europe	101057510
TwinAIR	Indoor air quality for healthy living	101057779
InChildHealth	Identifying determinants for indoor air quality and their health impact in environments for children: measures to improve indoor air quality and reduce disease burdens	101056883
Inquire	Identification of chemical and biological determinants, their sources, and strategies to promote healthier homes in Europe	101057499
EDIAQI	Evidence Driven Indoor Air Quality Improvement	101057497

Cluster's aim

To optimise synergies, avoid overlaps and increase the impact of the projects selected for funding under the call HORIZON-HLTH-2021-ENVHLTH-02-02 Indoor air quality and health, the projects have formed a cluster. Common cluster activities include the following:

1. Common cluster kick-off meeting of the six projects
2. Annual cluster meetings and periodic report of joint activities
3. Common dissemination and communication activities
4. Thematic workshops/trainings on issues of common interest
5. Working groups on topics of common interest
6. Advisory board

Document details

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Deliverable N°	-
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Purpose	This document outlines the common policy strategy for the IDEAL cluster. It identifies the main policy goals and stakeholders, as well as the key milestones and deliverables, to maximise the impact of the Cluster activities at the policy-making level.

Revision history

The following table describes the main changes done in the document since it was created.

REVISION	DATE	DESCRIPTION	AUTHOR (PROJECT)
V.0.1	14/07/2023	First draft	Panagiotis Chaslaridis, SynAir-G Valeria Ramiconi, SynAir-G Agata Papotto, SynAir-G Carla Viegas, InChildHealth Alex Borg, Ediaqi Jon Switters, Ediaqi
V.0.2	21/08/2023	Second draft	Panagiotis Chaslaridis, SynAir-G Valeria Ramiconi, SynAir-G Agata Papotto, SynAir-G
V.0.3	29/08/2023	Third Draft	Olympia Ageli, TwinAIR Stylios Karatzas, TwinAIR
V.1.0	29/08/2023	Final version	Panagiotis Chaslaridis, SynAir-G Valeria Ramiconi, SynAir-G Agata Papotto, SynAir-G

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2. IDEAL CLUSTER COMMON POLICY STRATEGY

2.1 Introduction

The Common **Policy Strategy** of the IDEAL Cluster is an activity jointly led by SynAir-G and K-HealthInAir projects, in collaboration with the wider Working Group on Science Translation for Policy and Practice (WG1).

This document details the IDEAL Cluster strategy and methodologies to implement effective policy actions in order to maximise the impact of the IDEAL Cluster and the individual projects of its members. Dissemination will be based on the activities and plans proposed by the Common Dissemination and Communication Strategy of the Cluster.

The common policy strategy provides an overview of the objectives, plans, timeline, activities and resources involved in the policy activities of the cluster.

2.2 Policy Aims and Strategy

The final objective of the IDEAL Cluster Common Policy Strategy is **the identification of recommendations to ensure the scientific translation of indoor air quality research into policy and practice and maximise the impact of the findings and results from the different projects.** Each policy brief will identify specific policy recommendation which will be consolidated as they are published and will be added in this document as an Annex. The recommendations as part of the policy brief will be then shared through the IDEAL Cluster channels as well as tools and outcomes of the document.

The Strategy entails several activities:

- The identification of relevant target groups (public and private bodies, civil society, stakeholders) at different levels of interest (international, national, regional, local) involved in (or affected by) the policy-making process, including:
 - Members of the European Parliament participating in relevant committees e.g. ENVI, ITRE etc.
 - Officials in relevant Commission services e.g. DG Environment, DG Energy, DG Research and Innovation etc.
 - Relevant national ministries e.g. of countries presiding the Council of the European Union
- Community building, to ensure a continuous interface among different projects and complementarity of work.
- The production and use of multidisciplinary evidence addressing barriers and real gaps to science translation while supporting decision-makers to transform society for the better.
- The identification of the key messages and findings to be translated for different policy levels, using the most relevant tools/actions for communication, dissemination and exploitation.
- The development of different channels for external communication of results, including dissemination events, social media, participation in conferences, policy briefs etc

2.3 Deliverables and Contribution

The IDEAL Cluster identified in the Working Group 1 “Science translation for policy and practices” the responsible organisations for the policy efforts of the cluster. Two projects, K-HealthInAir and SynAir-G are the co-leaders of the WG, but all the IDEAL Cluster projects members will contribute equally to the effort.

The working group will develop policy briefs and recommendations addressed to European and National authorities, to integrate the results of the cluster into policy strategies and initiatives, and influence the priorities of policy-makers, ensuring a timely uptake of the research findings.

In order to ensure an effective outreach of the policy-related deliverables, the WG1 will meet online at least once every semester to align on strategies, tasks and responsibilities. At the same time, additional ad hoc meetings can be organised to ensure the regular updates sharing as well as co-creation of the deliverables. After each meeting, a document with the minutes of the online session will be circulated among the WG1 members.

On the more operational side, an online shared folder will be provided to collect members inputs on the deliverables and work together on documents and their review.

Table 1: Working Group 1 Deliverables

Deliverable name	Lead partners	Contributing partners	Description	Due date
Cluster Policy Strategy	SynAirG K-HealthinAir	ALL	Definition of the 4-year strategy for the cluster to maximise the impact of the result of the 6 projects.	M12
Policy Briefs	SynAirG K-HealthinAir	ALL	Focused on science for policy communication / translation. Report on how the results of the cluster could contribute to policy strategies and initiatives.	M18 M32 M46

The key deliverables of this work are the three **Joint Policy Briefs**, which will focus on facilitating communication/translation of scientific evidence into policy and will report on how the results of the IDEAL Cluster could contribute to actual policy strategies and initiatives. The publication of the Joint Policy Briefs is foreseen as follows:

- March 2024, for the 1st Joint Policy Brief (JPB 1)
- July 2025, for the 2nd Joint Policy Brief (JPB 2)
- August 2026, for the 3rd Joint Policy Brief (JPB 3)

The WG1 reached a consensus on the approach the JPBs will adopt. The following approach was agreed:

- JPB 1 will provide a broad overview, defining the overarching issues linked to IAQ and the current situation of Indoor Air Quality in Europe. The focus will be to offer an outline of the objectives of the IDEAL Cluster projects. Stemming from these objectives, the JPB1 will aim to provide with key policy questions as well as recommendations.
- JPB 2 and JPB 3 will be more specific in nature, according to the advancements of the studies, the result of the research carried out and the identified gaps regarding IAQ. JPB 2 and JPB 3 will differ in scope from JPB 1, in the sense that they will aim to outline the main research findings that will be available by then. Nevertheless, like JPB 1, they will also seek to articulate specific recommendations for policy action.

All Joint Policy Briefs will be aligned with the scientific objectives of each project to ensure that they build on the scientific knowledge of research carried out in the individual projects. Their aim will be to act as a guide for policy-makers to understand pervasive issues linked to IAQ and to in turn foster more evidence-informed decisions. Furthermore, each project will also develop guidelines addressed to end users, policy-makers, and industry actors reflecting the findings of research from each individual project, including recommendations on pollutants. The joint work of the WG1 and WG4 will ensure the alignment of the final outcomes and deliverables.

To ensure a smooth, collaborative, and efficient working process, several meetings will be organised, including annual and periodic Cluster meetings as well as WG1 biannual meetings.

Thematic workshops/trainings will also contribute to the process as delineated in the IDEAL Cluster implementation plan. A policy component will in fact be present in every workshop organised by the

IDEAL Cluster, to ensure that this crucial part of the joint work is put forward and is made visible to internal and external stakeholders.

To reinforce outreach, the news about the publication of the JPBs will also be included in the Cluster's and projects' newsletters. Finally, the project partners leading this task within WG1 will explore possibilities for further dissemination in coordination with the WG3 (Communication and dissemination), for example through press releases.

2.4 EU and International policies linked to Indoor Air Quality

The IDEAL Cluster identified a series of EU-level and international policies looking at different aspects of IAQ. A tracker has been developed and made available to all Cluster members for their contribution. The tracker is a living document that will be updated during the duration of the IDEAL Cluster and beyond. The table below provides a non-exhaustive list of several identified policies:

Table 2: EU and international policies related to indoor air quality

Name	Aim
Zero Pollution Action Plan	Improve air quality, reduce the number of premature deaths caused by air pollution by 55% by 2030
Ambient Air Quality Directives (2008-under revision)	Improve air quality by setting concentration limits and common measurement methods for certain pollutants
EU Renovations Wave initiative (2020)	Boost renovations in Europe
Directive 2018/844 on the Energy Performance of Buildings (2018-under revision)	Decrease the environmental and climate footprint of the EU building sector, accelerate renovations
New European Bauhaus initiative (2020)	Enhance quality of life and health within built environments
EU Regulation 305/2011 for the Marketing of Construction Products (2011-under revision)	Establish harmonised standards to assess the performance of construction products
EU Directive 2004/37/EC on Carcinogens, Mutagens and reprotoxic substances directive (2004-revised on a rolling basis)	Protect workers from the risks related to exposure to carcinogens, mutagens or reprotoxic substances at work
Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) (2006 – under revision)	Improve the protection of human health and the environment from the risks that can be posed by chemicals
Directive for the exposure to asbestos at work (2009 – under revision)	Protect workers health from risk of asbestos exposure, via limit values and specific requirements
WHO Air Quality Guidelines (2021)	Provide evidence-based recommendations on the levels of air pollutants in relation to critical health outcomes

[WHO fungal priority pathogens list to guide research, development and public health action](#) (WHO FPPL) (2022)

First global effort to systematically prioritize fungal pathogens, considering their unmet research and development (R&D) needs and perceived public health importance. The WHO FPPL aims to focus and drive further research and policy interventions to strengthen the global response to fungal infections and antifungal resistance.

2.5 Stakeholders mapping and engagement

The IDEAL Cluster developed a **stakeholder map**, with actors from various sectors such as health, education, science, construction and policy/civil society, including internal dissemination channels to facilitate the outreach and to mainstream IAQ importance. The list of relevant stakeholders from the area of industry, and civil society at both the EU and international level, is also a living document that can be accessed by the IDEAL Cluster members via the internal repository throughout the duration project. The final list with the relevant stakeholders will be used for dissemination of the policy briefs and other relevant policy related activities of the IDEAL Cluster.

2.6 Communication and Dissemination

The IDEAL Cluster has put forward a Communication and Dissemination Strategy detailing the various activities involved and their objectives. This will ensure an effective outreach vis-a-vis policy-related deliverables. The plan includes:

- The identification of primary and secondary target audience within the indoor air quality ecosystem, including academia, policymakers, industry associations, EU authorities, and the general public.
- The creation of an internal communication channel, including tools such as a common repository platform, an internal newsletter, and various distribution lists and internal events.
- Details on external communication channels and tools, including the website, newsletter, social media channels together with the rules and guidelines for using them.

Importantly, the plan foresees a series of events to support the dissemination of the policy outcomes of all the projects across the IDEAL Cluster as well as relevant stakeholders, including the wider public. In addition, each project composing the IDEAL Cluster has public events planned. Although the initiatives may emerge from individual projects, all Cluster members will be involved, to ensure that the dissemination of IDEAL Cluster findings and results are fully leveraged. Examples of these events include:

- SynAir-G launch event for policy recommendations at the European Parliament (October 2025): this event will be linked to the publication of the 2nd Joint Policy Brief.
- Joint Final conference (October 2026): this event will showcase the final Cluster projects' results and policy recommendations and will include academia, health care professionals, civil society as well as policy-makers.
- Newsletters to be developed under the WG3 scope.

2.7 Synergies with other EU projects and initiatives

The 7 projects involved in the IDEAL Cluster often foster synergies with projects falling under other EU research programmes. The aim is to build a common research space and avoid overlaps while also increasing the impact of these projects, and therefore maximising the usability of the evidence in policymaking. Some examples include:

- [European Human Exposome Network](#) (EHEN), which aims to protect citizens' health and wellbeing from pollution and environmental deterioration by providing new evidence for better preventive policies.
- [Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals](#) (PARC), which aims to develop next-generation chemical risk assessment in order to protect health and the environment.
- [Urban Health Cluster](#), which aims to improve and safeguard health and well-being of citizens, specifically focusing on urban areas.
- [Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring](#) (IPCHEM), in the context of the WG2 activities

Suggestion to rephrase a bit: The synergies with other projects will be fostered through multiple channels, including by inviting other projects' representatives to IDEAL Cluster events and workshops. In addition, as some IDEAL Cluster partners are also involved in some of the listed initiatives, we expect that there will be ample space for sharing knowledge and latest updates. These interactions will offer the opportunity to maximise the outreach, strengthen the impact and enable the exchange of good practices both within the Cluster and externally.

ANNEX I

Translation of indoor air quality research into policy Recommendations of the IDEAL Cluster